

TEA AS THE BEST MEDIUM FOR THE GROWTH OF KOMBUCHA

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This task is a substitute task for the final semester exam in 2022 with lecturer Muhammad Nazri Janra, M.Si, M.A. This paper concerns the science of microbiology and biochemistry which discusses what media is best for the growth of kombucha. Kombucha is a fermented product using *Acetobacter* bacteria and several types of yeast as the starter. The medium used is quite diverse, such as tea water, rosella, guava leaves, betel leaves, cocoa powder solution and many more. Each medium has a different chemical content that affects the growth of kombucha. This discussion is quite interesting to me because this topic combines microbiology with biochemistry. In addition, many people, including me, still don't know much about kombucha so the discussion of this topic is quite new and not many have reviewed it, even though kombucha has a myriad of benefits especially for health.

Kombucha is the result of the fermentation of tea and sugar by a kombucha culture starter called SCOBY. Symbiosis of kombucha cultures include *Acetobacter*, namely *Acetobacter xylinum*, and several types of yeast, namely *Brettanomyces*, *Zygosaccharomyces*, and *Saccharomyces* (Mayser *et al*, 1995). The major components produced during fermentation are acetic acid, ethanol, and glucuronic acid, while the minor components produced are lactic acid, phenolic acid, B vitamins, and enzymes. Kombucha also contains organic compounds that are beneficial to the body, namely vitamin B complex, organic acids, and other compounds that function as antibiotics (Naland, 2008). Kombucha has various health effects, including as an antibiotic, promoting digestion, antioxidants, and antibacterials (Chen & Chu, 2006).

Kombucha can also be made from types of plants that contain alkaloids such as coffee, cocoa, and tea. Alkaloids are the largest group of secondary metabolite compounds in plants that have many benefits for health and as medicinal plants, namely as antioxidants. In addition, alkaloid has an effect on the field of health in the form of triggers of the nervous system, raising blood pressure, reducing pain, antimicrobials, sedatives, heart disease drugs. Alkaloids can be used as a competitive support for the work of *A. xylinum* in the process of growing kombucha. Based on the research of Nur *et al* (2018), the total bacteria of *A. xylinum* in powdered brown kombucha is quite high, which is 36.25×10^7 cfu / ml. The total magnitude of *A. xylinum* bacteria in cocoa leaf Kombucha is due to the fact that nutrients are available in the optimal range for its growth. *A. xylinum* will utilize sugar in growth. Cocoa contains various bioactivity of bioflavonoid antioxidant compounds such as polyphenols, monomers as well as Oligomers ProCianidin (OPC), catechins, epicatechins (Syukur *et al*, 2009). In addition, in cocoa (especially the pulp) In addition to the presence of indigenous microbiota, cocoa also contains nutrients needed for microbial fermentation metabolism (Indrayati *et al*, 2021). Thus, cocoa is an excellent medium for microbial growth. Although cocoa is quite well used as a medium for growing kombucha, tea media is still the best for kombucha growth. Kombucha with cocoa media is superior in taste, while in tea media microbes can adapt well and produce the best results because of the tannins contained in tea.

Another type of plant that is beneficial to health besides kombucha is a type of foliage that contains phenols so that it can be used as a functional drink. Foliage that contains phenols as antioxidants include tea leaves, guava leaves, coffee leaves, soursop leaves, bay leaves, and betel leaves. Guava leaves contain antioxidants, namely tannins, polyphenolates, flavonoids, monoterpenoids, cystulents, alkaloids, quinones, saponins, carotene, essential oils (eugenol), and fatty oils (Kurniawati, 2006). Coffee leaves contain antioxidant alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids and polyphenols. Coffee leaves are plantation waste that is usually used for coffee leaf tea. Soursop leaves contain antioxidants and are believed by the Indonesian people as herbal medicine to treat cancer (Leny, 2006). Bay leaf contains tannins, essential oils, sesquiterpenes, triterpenoids, phenols, steroids, sitral, lactones, saponins, and carbohydrates that have the potential to produce antioxidant activity (BPOM, 2004). Betel leaf is a medicinal plant that is believed by the public to relieve pain so it is called analgesic medicine (Karlisna, 2010). While the tea leaves contain flavonoid antioxidants which are part of polyphenols. The increase in antioxidant activity is due to the presence of free phenolic produced during the fermentation process, so that the higher the phenolic level produced, the higher the antioxidant activity (Bhanja *et al*, 2009). Thus of the many types of leaves already mentioned, tea leaves are the best for the growth of kombucha.

The success of a Kombucha fermentation is largely determined by the activity of the bacteria *A. xylinum* as evidenced by the thickness of the nata produced. The weak and less competitive work of *A. xylinum* is caused by unsuitable fermentation media and inappropriate environmental conditions (Nur *et al*, 2018). Based on research by Suhardini & Elok (2016), the raw materials used in his research include young coffee leaves of robusta coffee type, young guava leaves, young soursop leaves, young bay leaves, young tea leaves, and young betel leaves. The thickest

nata is obtained in kombucha made of Guava leaves with a thickness of 0.50 mm. While the thinnest nata is produced in kombucha made of Betel leaves with a thickness of 0.20 mm. The thinness of nata produced in betel leaves is in betel leaves providing many of bioactive compound as medicinal resources (Putri & Noli, 2021). This leads to inhibition of microbial growth so that it cannot produce new cellulose. In addition, the nata produced by tea leaves is also quite thick, which is 0.45 mm. The difference of 0.5 mm in the thickness of guava leaf nata with tea leaf nata is thought to be caused by factors such as the longer the fermentation time, the nutrients contained in the tea solution will be used by bacteria and yeast to metabolize and form new colonies that cause nata thickness.

Thus it can be concluded that tea is the best medium for the growth of kombucha. The content in tea such as pH, total acid, total phenol, total sugar, antioxidant activity, thickness of nata produced and so on are the main reasons tea is the best medium for kombucha. In addition, kombucha has a myriad of health benefits, including antibiotics, promoting digestion, antioxidants, and antibacterials. There is still very little research related to kombucha, so there is still little knowledge of the many other potential benefits contained in kombucha.

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